

Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Species Collected by Light Trap in Diyarbakır (Türkiye)

Meral Fent¹Halil Bolu²Suat Kiyak³

¹Trakya University, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology, 22030, Edirne/ Türkiye. E-mail: m_fent@hotmail.com ORCID id: 0000-0001-5787-6714

²Dicle University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Plant Protection, TR 21280, Diyarbakır, TÜRKİYE, E-mail: besni@dicle.edu.tr, ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5488-0056

³Gazi University, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology, 06500, Ankara/Türkiye E-mail: skiyak@gazi.edu.tr ORCID id: 0000-0001-8167-8283

ABSTRACT: As a result of the evaluation of the material collected by Robinson light trap in Diyarbakır Province, Sur district located in the south-east Türkiye between May–September 2015, 56 species belonging to 13 families of Heteroptera were determined. Among these species, *Camptocera glaberrima* (Walker, 1872), *Nysius cymoides* (Spinola, 1837), *Reduvius ciliatus* Jakovlev, 1879, *Megalonotus colon* Puton, 1874, *Tropistethus lanternae* Linnavuori, 1960, *Sigara lateralis* (Leach, 1817), *Beosus quaripunctatus* (Müller, 1766) and *Geotomus elongatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840) are common species. In addition, Heteroptera species previously detected in light trap studies in Türkiye are given in a table for comparison purposes. *Mecidea lindbergi* Wagner, 1954 is recorded for the second time from Türkiye.

KEYWORDS: Heteroptera, light trap, Diyarbakır, Türkiye

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INTRODUCTION

Light is attractive to some Heteroptera species as well as to many insect groups. In Türkiye, there are a few studies on Heteroptera obtained by use of light traps. The first of these is the study

published by Hoberlandt (1961) in which 37 species were identified and this study is based on the materials collected by F. S. Bodenheimer from Ankara between 1940-1941. Later, Önder & Adıgüzel (1979) identified 87 species belonging to 13 families in the study in Diyarbakır.

Following this, Önder et al. (1981) determined 155 species belonging to 15 families as a result of the evaluation of the material collected with light traps in 5 provinces (İstanbul, Kocaeli, Bursa, Sakarya and Bolu) in northwestern Anatolia. Önder et al. (1984) determined 128 species belonging to 12 families obtained with light traps in Edirne province of Thrace Region, between 1978–1981. Yıldırım et al. (1999) determined 57 heteropteran species belonging to 5 families in the study in Erzurum province, in the eastern Türkiye. And finally, Tezcan et al. (2010) recorded 35 species belonging to 8 families collected by light trap in cherry orchards in İzmir of the western Anatolian province.

Light traps, which are derived from the attractive effect of light on insects, have been used by entomologists as an effective collecting method for long time, especially for some groups or species. In this study, Heteroptera samples collected by light trap in Diyarbakır were identified and also Heteroptera species that were detected with the sampling method by light trap in Türkiye so far were shown on a table. We believe that this study will give an idea to researchers working on Heteroptera that the use of light traps will be beneficial, especially to collect some families or species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted with Robinson type light trap at Dicle University, Faculty of Agriculture Campus in Diyarbakır, Sur district (667 m, 37°53'20.5"N 40°16'18.6"E) between May and September of 2015 year. 20 W Philips lamp was used in the light trap. The light trap was placed approximately 90 cm above the ground in the campus area (Figure 1) and was checked until mid-September.

Heteroptera samples caught by this method were preserved in alcohol tubes. When the habitat characteristics of the study area take into consideration, it is seen that there are false acacia, pine, apricot and various fruit trees, vineyards and agricultural lands planted for trial purposes (Figure 2). It is also located in

approximately 2 km from the Dicle (Tigris) River.

A list of species, which includes data belonging collection dates and individual numbers, obtained in this study was given in Table 1. Furthermore, the Heteroptera species list, which was detected in previous studies conducted with light traps in Türkiye, was presented in Table 2.

RESAULTS

ANTHOCORIDAE

Anthocoris visci Douglas, 1889

16.07.2015, 1 ♀.

ARTHENEIDAE

Holcocranum saturejae (Kolenati, 1845)

06.08.2015, 2 ♀♀.

BLISSIDAE

Ischnodemus caspius Jakovlev, 1871

09.07.2015, 3 ♀♀; 24.07.2015, 1 ♀.

CORIXIDAE

Sigara lateralis (Leach, 1817)

02.07.2015, 28 ♀♀, 20 ♂♂; 09.07.2015, 9 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂; 16.07.2015, 5 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; 24.07.2015, 21 ♀♀, 20 ♂♂; 30.07.2015, 1 ♂; 20.08.2015, 1 ♂; 26.08.2015, 19 ♀♀, 19 ♂♂; 17.09.2015, 5 ♀♀.

CYDNIDAE

Byrsinus pilosulus (Klug, 1845)

20.08.2015, 1 ♀.

Geotomus elongatus (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)

09.07.2015, 6 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; 16.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 24.07.2015, 1 ♀, 5 ♂♂; 15.08.2015, 1 ♀; 26.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

Macroscytus brunneus (Fabricius, 1803)

16.07.2015, 2 ♀♀; 30.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; 06.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 20.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

LYGAEIDAE***Nysius cymoides* (Spinola, 1837)**

21.05.2015, 7 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 02.07.2015, 14 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; 09.07.2015 numerous; 16.07.2015, numerous; 24.07.2015, numerous; 30.07.2015, numerous; 06.08.2015, numerous; 15.08.2015, 25 ♀♀, 10 ♂; 26.08.2015, 128 ♀♀, 64 ♂♂.

MIRIDAE***Adelphocoris quadripunctatus* (Fabricius, 1794)**

24.07.2015, 1 ♂.

***Alloeotomus cyprius* (Wagner, 1953)**

02.07.2015, 1 ♀.

***Campylomma diversicorne* Reuter, 1888**

02.07.2015, 1 ♂; 15.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

***Campylomma verbasci* Poppius, 1914**

28.05.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

***Creontiodes pallidus* (Rambur, 1839)**

15.08.2015, 1 ♂.

***Deraeocoris punctulatus* (Fallén, 1807)**

28.05.2015, 1 ♀.

***Deraeocoris rutilus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)**

20.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

***Deraeocoris serenus* (Douglas & Scott, 1868)**

28.05.2015, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 06.08.2015, 3 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 1 ♀.

***Dicyphus albonasatus* Wagner, 1951**

02.07.2015, 1 ♀.

***Lygus pratensis* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

21.05.2015, 6 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; 28.05.2015, 1 ♀; 02.07.2015, 1 ♀; 09.07.2015, 1 ♀; 16.07.2015, 1 ♀; 24.07.2015, 9 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 1 ♀.

***Lygus gemellatus* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

24.07.2015, 6 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂.

***Macrolophus pygmaeus* (Rambur, 1839)**

28.05.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 02.07.2015, 1 ♂; 06.08.2015 1 ♂.

***Oncotylus anatolicus* Wagner, 1969**

28.05.2015, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

***Oncotylus nigricornis* Saunders, 1876**

28.05.2015, 9 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂; 02.07.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

***Oncotylus viridiflavus* (Goeze, 1778)**

28.05.2015, 1 ♀, 4 ♂♂.

***Stenodema turanica* Reuter, 1904**

16.07.2015, 1 ♂.

***Stenodema virens* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

30.07.2015, 1 ♀, 06.08.2015, 1 ♂.

***Trigonotylus pulchellus* (Hahn, 1834)**

02.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂; 09.07.2015, 12 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂.

NABIDAE***Nabis ferus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

24.07.2015, 3 ♀♀; 30.07.2015, 5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 06.08.2015, 2 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 1 ♂.

***Nabis pseudoferus* Remane, 1949**

16.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂.

***Nabis rugosus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

24.07.2015, 1 ♂.

NOTONECTIDAE***Notonecta viridis* Delcourt, 1909**

16.07.2015, 1 ♂.

PENTATOMIDAE***Acrosternum breviceps* (Jakovlev, 1889)**

30.07.2015, 2 ♀♀; 06.08.2015, 1 ♀.

***Mecidea lindbergi* Wagner, 1954**

02.07.2015, 1 ♀; 20.08.2015, 1 ♂; 26.08.2015, 1 ♀.

***Stagonomus bipunctatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

02.07.2015, 1 ♀.

REDUVIIDAE

Ectomocoris caucasicus Linnavuori, 1972

24.07.2015, 1 ♀; 20.08.2015, 2 ♀♀;
26.08.2015 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀.

Ectomocoris ululans (Rossi, 1790)

24.07.2015 1 ♂.

Nagusta goedeli (Kolenati, 1857)

09.07.2015, 1 ♀.

Oncocephalus squalidus (Rossi, 1790)

21.05.2015, 1 ♀.

Pasira marinadolina Putshkov & Moulet, 2003

21.05.2015, 1 ♀.

Peirates hybridus (Scopoli, 1763)

30.07.2015, 1 ♀.

Reduvius ciliatus Jakovlev, 1879

28.05.2015, 1 ♂; 02.07.2015, 4 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂;
09.07.2015, 2 ♂♂; 16.07.2015, 1 ♀, 5 ♂♂;
24.07.2015, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; 30.07.2015, 2 ♀♀,
2 ♂♂; 06.08.2015, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; 15.08.2015,
6 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 5 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂,
17.09.2015, 4 ♀♀, 6 ♂♂.

Reduvius iracundus (Poda, 1761)

20.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

RHOPALIDAE

Liorhyssus hyalinus (Fabricius, 1794)

09.07.2015, 1 ♀.

Rhopalus parampunctatus Schilling, 1829

24.07.2015, 1 ♀.

RHYPAROCHROMIDAE

Beosus quadripunctatus (Müller, 1766)

28.05.2015, 3 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 02.07.2015, 5 ♀♀,
4 ♂♂; 09.07.2015, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂;
24.07.2015, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 30.07.2015 1 ♂;
06.08.2015, 2 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂; 17.09.2015 1 ♂.

Camptocera glaberrima (Walker, 1872)

02.07.2015, 3 ♀♀; 09.07.2015, numerous;
16.07.2015, 16 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂; 24.07.2015, nu-
merous; 30.07.2015, numerous;
06.08.2015, numerous; 15.08.2015, 1 ♀,
1 ♂; 20.08.2015, 17 ♀♀, 8 ♂♂;
26.08.2015, 4 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

Emblethis verbasci (Fabricius, 1803)

24.07.2015, 2 ♂♂.

Ischnopeza pallipes Puton, 1892

30.07.2015, 2 ♂♂.

Lethaeus cribratissimus (Stål, 1859)

24.07.2015, 1 ♀.

Lethaeus nitidus (Douglas & Scott, 1868)

09.07.2015, 1 ♂.

Megalonotus colon Puton, 1874

02.07.2015, 1 ♂; 09.07.2015, 5 ♀♀, 1 ♂;
24.07.2015, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂; 30.07.2015, 8 ♀♀,
14 ♂♂; 06.08.2015, 1 ♀, 3 ♂♂;
15.08.2015, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; 20.08.2015, 2 ♀♀;
26.08.2015, 1 ♀.

Megalonotus maximus (Puton, 1895)

24.07.2015, 1 ♀; 30.07.2015, 1 ♀.

Megalonotus sabulicola (Thomson, 1870)

06.08.2015, 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂.

Neurocladus brachiidens (Dufour, 1851)

09.07.2015, 3 ♀♀; 4 ♂♂; 16.07.2015, 2 ♀♀;
24.07.2015, 2 ♀♀; 30.07.2015, 2 ♂♂.

Peritrechus flavicornis Jakovlev, 1877

09.07.2015, 1 ♂; 30.07.2015, 3 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂;
06.08.2015, 3 ♂♂.

Tropistethus lanternae Linnavuori, 1960

09.07.2015, 14 ♀♀, 5 ♂♂; 16.07.2015, 1 ♀,
2 ♂♂; 24.07.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 30.07.2015,
5 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; 26.08.2015, 1 ♀, 1 ♂;
17.09.2015, 3 ♀♀.

Xanthochilus saturnius (Rossi, 1790)

24.07.2015 1 ♂; 06.08.2015 2 ♀♀, 1 ♂;
20.08.2015, 1 ♀.

DISCUSSION

As a result of the evaluation of Heteroptera samples collected with Robinson light trap between May and September 2015 in Diyarbakır, Sur district, a total of 56 species from 13 families were identified. The distribution of determined species in families is as follows: Anthocoridae 1 species, Artheneidae 1 species, Bilissidae 1 species, Corixidae 1 species, Cydnidae 3 species, Lygaeidae 1 species, Miridae 18 species, Nabidae 3 species, Notonectidae 1 species, Pentatomidae 3 species, Reduviidae 8 species, Rhopalidae 2 species and Rhyparochromidae 13 species (Table 1). Considering that the most captured species in the light trap belong to the families Miridae, Rhyparochromidae and Reduviidae, respectively, these numbers coincide with the general species numbers of the families.

Among the detected species, *Reduvius ciliatus* (Reduviidae) is the most sensitive to light, as it was detected in 10 of the 12 collection periods. Similarly, *Camptocera glaberrima* (Rhyparochromidae) and *Nysius cymoides* (Lygaeidae) were found in 9 of 12 collection periods. In addition, these two species have very high numbers of specimens, especially in the period between 9 July and 6 August. Other common species are *Megalonotus colon*, *Tropistethus lanternae* and *Beosus quaripunctatus* (all Rhyparochromidae), *Sigara lateralis* (Corixidae) and *Geotomus elongatus* (Cydnidae).

Considering the results of this study and the other light traps studies conducted on Heteroptera in Türkiye (Hoberlandt, 1961; Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 1981, 1984; Yıldırım et al. 1999 and Tezcan et al., 2010) 305 species belonging to 25 families from Heteroptera are listed (Table 2.). When these species take into account, some of them are remarkable in that they come to the light traps.

Considering the results of the present study and 6 studies conducted previously, *Campylomma verbasci*, *Deraeocoris serenus*, *Lygus pratensis* and *Macrolophus pygmaeus* species were found in 6 of 7

studies; *Nysius cymoides*, *N. graminicola*, *graminicola*, *Adelphocoris lineolatus*, *Nanopsallus carduellus*, *Oncotylus setulosus*, *Oncotylus viridiflavus*, *Polymerus cognatus*, *Nabis pseudoferus* and *Peirates hybridus* in 5 studies and *Macroscytus brunneus*, *Campylomma diversicornis*, *Charagochilus gyllenhalii*, *Megalocoleus molliculus*, *Plagiognathus bipunctatus*, *P. fulvipennis*, *Polymerus vulneratus*, *Trigonotylus pulchellus*, *T. ruficornis*, *Tuponia hippophaes*, *Acrosternum millierei*, *Eysarcoris ventralis*, *Beosus quadripunctatus* and *Lamprodema maura* in 4 studies.

Among these common species, *Deraeocoris serenus*, *Lygus pratensis* ve *Macrolophus pygmaeus*, *Nysius cymoides*, *Oncotylus viridiflavus*, *Macroscytus brunneus*, *Nabis pseudoferus*, *Peirates hybridus*, *Campylomma diversicornis*, *Trigonotylus pulchellus*, *Eysarcoris ventralis* and *Beosus quadripunctatus* were also identified in the present study.

Unlike other light trap studies in Türkiye, *Anthocoris visci*, *Ischnodemus caspius*, *Sigara lateralis*, *Byrsinus pilosulus*, *Adelphocoris quadripunctatus*, *Alloeotomus cyprius*, *Creontiodes pallidus*, *Oncotylus anaticus*, *O. nigricornis*, *Nabis fesus*, *Notonecta viridis*, *Mecidea lindbergi*, *Ectomocoris caucasicus*, *E. ululans*, *Nagusta goedeli*, *Pasira marinadolina*, *Rhopalus parampunctatus*, *Ischnopeza pallipes*, *Lethaeus cribratissimus*, *L. nitidus*, *Megalonotus colon*, *M. maximus*, *Neurocladus brachiidens*, *Peritrechus flavicornis*, *Tropistethus lanternae* and *Xanthochilus saturnius* are Heteroptera species caught in light trap for the first time in this study.

In addition, *Mecidea lindbergi* previously recorded from Siirt by Özgen & Çerçi (2018) from Türkiye, was recorded for the second time from Türkiye in this study. Among other recorded species, *Oncotylus anaticus*, *Acrosternum breviceps*, *Pasira marinadolina*, *Reduvius ciliatus*, *Lethaeus nitidus*, *Megalonotus maximus*, *Tropistethus lanternae* and *Peritrechus flavicornis* are species with rare distribution.

REFERENCES

- Hoberlandt, L., 1961, Heteroptera collected in Ankara (Türkiye) by light trap. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae*, 34(590): 399-416.
- Önder, F. & Adıgüzel, N., 1979, Some Heteroptera collected by light trap in Diyarbakır (Türkiye). *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 3(1): 25-34.
- Önder F., Ünal A., Ünal, E., 1981, Heteroptera fauna collected by light traps in some districts of Northwestern part of Anatolia. *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 5(3): 151-169.
- Önder, F., Ünal, A., Ünal, E., 1984: Heteropterous insects collected by light traps in Edirne. *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi*, 8 (4): 215-224.
- Özgen, İ., Çerçi, B., 2018, First record of the narrow stink bug *Mecidea lindbergi* Wagner 1954 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Mecideini) from Türkiye. *Ecologia Balkanica*, 10(1): 53-56.
- Tezcan, S., Gülperçin, N., Fent, M., 2010, Contribution to the knowledge of the light trap collected Heteroptera fauna occurring in cherry orchards in western Türkiye. *Linzer biologische Beiträge*, 42(1): 817-823.
- Yıldırım, E., Özbek, H., Önder, F., 1999, Heteropterous species caught in light traps in the Campus of Ataturk University in Erzurum (Türkiye). *Türkiye Entomoloji Dergisi*, 23 (3): 225-228.

Figure 1. Satellite image of the research area (Google earth) (yellow star marks the spot where the light trap was placed)

Figure 2. View of the research area from different angles

Table 1. Heteroptera species list with collection dates and individual numbers obtained in this study. (N:numerous)

Species/Datum	21.05	28.05	02.07	09.07	16.07	24.07	30.07	06.08	15.08	20.08	26.08	17.09
ANTHOCORIDAE												
<i>Anthocoris visci</i> Douglas, 1889					1							
ARTHENEIDAE												
<i>Holocranum saturejae</i> (Kolenati, 1845)								2				
BILISSIDAE												
<i>Ischnodemus caspius</i> Jakovlev, 1871				3		1						
CORIXIDAE												
<i>Sigara lateralis</i> (Leach, 1817)			48	15	13	41	1			1	38	5
CYDNIDAE												
<i>Byrsinus pilosulus</i> (Klug, 1845)										1		
<i>Geotomus elongatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)				11	4	6			1			6
<i>Macroscytus brunneus</i> (Fabricius, 1803)					2		3	2			5	
LYGAEIDAE												
<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola 1834)	10		24	61	N	N	N	N	3			192
MIRIDAE												
<i>Adelphocoris quadripunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)										1		
<i>Alloeotomus cyprinus</i> (Wagner, 1953)			1									
<i>Campylomma diversicornis</i> Reuter, 1878			1						8			
<i>Campylomma verbasci</i> Poppius, 1914			5									
<i>Creontiodes pallidus</i> (Rambur, 1839)									1			

Table 1. Continued

REDUVIIDAE												
<i>Ectomocoris caucasicus</i> Linnavuori, 1972										1		3
<i>Ectomocoris ululans</i> (Rossi, 1790)										1		
<i>Nagusta goedei</i> (Kolenati, 1857)						1						
<i>Oncocephalus squalidus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	1											
<i>Psira marinadolina</i> Putshkov & Moullet, 2003	1											
<i>Peirates hybridus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)									1			
<i>Reduvius ciliatus</i> Ja- kovlev, 1879	1	7	2	6	6	6	4	3	11	15	10	
<i>Reduvius iracundus</i> (Poda, 1761)										2		
RHOPALIDAE												
<i>Liorhyssus hyalinus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)						1						
<i>Rhopalus parampunctatus</i> Schilling, 1829										1		
RHYPAROCHROMIDAE												
<i>Beosus quadripunctatus</i> (Muller, 1766)		5	9	6	6	6	1	5				1
<i>Campitocera glaberrima</i> (Walker 1872)			3	N	24	N	N	N	2	25	6	
<i>Emblethis verbasci</i> (Fabricius, 1803)						2						
<i>Ischnopeza pallipes</i> Puton, 1892									2			
<i>Lethaeus cribratissimus</i> (Stål, 1859)							1					
<i>Lethaeus nitidus</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)					1							
<i>Megalonotus colon</i> Pu- ton, 1874			1	6	4	4	22	4	3	2	1	

Table 2. Heteroptera species list obtained in previous light trap studies and this study in Türkiye

Heteroptera species / Studies	Hoberlandt (1961)	Önder & Adigüzel (1979)	Önder et al. (1981)	Önder et al. (1984)	Yildirim et al. (1999)	Tezcan et al. (2010)	This study
ANTHOCORIDAE							
<i>Anthocoris visci</i> Douglas, 1889							+
<i>Lytocoris dimidiatus</i> (Spinola, 1837)			+	+			
<i>Orius horvathi</i> (Reuter, 1884)				+			
<i>Orius laevigatus</i> (Fieber, 1860)		+		+			
<i>Orius majusculus</i> (Reuter, 1879)				+			
<i>Orius minutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			+				
<i>Orius niger</i> (Wolff, 1811)		+		+			
<i>Orius laticollis</i> (Reuter, 1884)		+					
ARTHENEIDAE							
<i>Artheneis balcanica</i> (Kormilev, 1938)			+				
<i>Holocorannum satyrejae</i> (Kolenati, 1845)			+	+			+
BERYTIDAE							
<i>Gampsocoris punctipes</i> (Germar, 1822)			+				
BILISSIDAE							
<i>Ischnodemus caspius</i> Jakovlev, 1871							+
COREIDAE							
<i>Centrocoris variegatus</i> Kolenati, 1845						+	
<i>Coreus marginatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)						+	
<i>Contomeris hirticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)		+					

Table 2. Continued

CORIXIDAE									
<i>Corixa affinis</i> Leach, 1817									
<i>Corixa panzeri</i> Fieber, 1848								+	
<i>Corixa punctata</i> (Illiger, 1807)								+	
<i>Helicorisa vermiculata</i> (Puton, 1874)							+?		
<i>Hesperocorixa linnaei</i> (Fieber, 1848)							+		
<i>Hesperocorixa parallela</i> (Fieber, 1860)							+		
<i>Paracorixa concinna</i> (Fieber, 1848)								+	
<i>Sigara lateralis</i> (Leach, 1817)									+
<i>Sigara nigrolineata</i> (Fieber, 1848)							+	+	
<i>Sigara striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)								+	
CYDNIDAE									
<i>Byrsinus pilosulus</i> (Klug, 1845)									+
<i>Canthophorus dubius</i> (Scopoli, 1763)								+	
<i>Geotomus elongatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840)								+	+
<i>Macroscytus brunneus</i> (Fabricius, 1803)								+	+
<i>Sehirus morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)								+	
CYMIDAE									
<i>Cymus clavicornis</i> (Fallén, 1807)								+	
<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861								+	
GEOCORIDAE									
<i>Geocoris arenarius</i> (Jakovlev, 1867)								+	
<i>Geocoris megacephalus</i> (Rossi, 1790)								+	

Table 2. Continued

LEPTOPODIDAE										
<i>Patapius spinosus</i> (Rossi, 1790)									+	
LYGAEIDAE										
<i>Arocatus longiceps</i> Stål, 1872										+
<i>Horvathiolus superbus</i> (Pollich, 1781)									+	
<i>Kleidocerys ericae</i> (Horváth, 1908)										+
<i>Kleidocerys resedae resedae</i> (Panzer, 1797)										+
<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola 1834)									+	
<i>Nysius graminicola graminicola</i> (Kolenati, 1845)									+	
<i>Nysius immuris</i> (Walker, 1872)									+	
<i>Nysius helveticus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)									+	
<i>Nysius senecionis</i> (Schilling, 1829)									+	
<i>Nysius thymi thymi</i> (Wolff, 1804)									+	
<i>Ortholomus carinatus</i> (Lindberg, 1932)									+	
MICRONECTIDAE										
<i>Micronecta griseola</i> Horváth, 1899										+
<i>Micronecta scholtzi</i> (Fieber, 1860)										+
MIRIDAE										
<i>Acrothium conspersum</i> Noualhier, 1895									+	
<i>Adelphocoris bimaculicollis</i> Lindberg, 1948									+	
<i>Adelphocoris insignis</i> Horváth, 1898										+
<i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)									+	
<i>Adelphocoris seticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)									+	

